

Use of lanthanum cerate ternary oxide as a novel photocatalyst for removal of brilliant green from aqueous solution

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In the present work, removal of brilliant green from its aqueous solution via photocatalytic reduction has been carried out using ternary catalyst lanthanum cerate under visible light. The catalyst was synthesized by citric acid assisted sol-gel method. Characterization of synthesized catalyst has been carried by XRD, SEM, TEM, FTIR, EDS, TG-DTA. The rate of degradation of dye was monitored spectrophotometrically by measuring absorbance of dye solution at regular time intervals. The effect of various parameters such as pH, concentration of dye, photocatalyst dosage and light intensity has been studied on the rate of degradation. Water quality parameters such as chemical oxygen demand (COD), conductance, pH, TDS, salinity and dissolved oxygen (DO) for the reaction mixture have also been determined before and after degradation. A tentative mechanism for degradation of dye has been proposed involving superoxide anions radicals. Reusability of catalyst has been assessed.

Keywords: Brilliant green, lanthanum cerate, photocatalyst, ternary catalyst.

Introduction

Water is one of the most important natural resource on the globe essential for all life forms. With the development of modern industries and population growth, the environment pollution caused by hazardous wastes is becoming a serious global problem. Water pollution is a major global problem. It is estimated that around 10–15% of organic dyes are discharged directly into environment leading to a hazardous impact on public health and the environment, even when they are present in very low concentrations^{1,2}. Dyes have been used widely in various industries like textile, photography, coating and in photochemical applications³. The color in the wastewater is an obvious indicator of water pollution due to dyes and pigments^{4,5}. Dyes in water also affect photosynthetic activity of aquatic plants due to reduced light penetration and may be toxic to some aquatic lives⁶. The most common methods used for the treatment of effluents from dyeing industries are membrane filtration, coagulation-flocculation, biological treatment, catalytic oxidation, sorption

process, ion exchange etc. These treatment methods for the removal of dyes from the wastewater suffer from disadvantage of generation of some secondary pollutants. Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) have been successful in treating most of the refractory organic compounds present in polluted water. The reason for the use of AOPs is due to the inability of conventional processes to treat highly contaminated toxic water⁷. Presently, photocatalysis, one of the important AOP, has become an emerging technology for treatment of wastewater generating worldwide. Photocatalysis can be used to destroy dyes and organic pollutants using semiconductor under light irradiation⁸. An important advantage of photocatalytic process is that these may be carried out at low or ambient temperature and usually leads to the complete mineralization of pollutants⁹.

Aguiar *et al.*¹⁰ reported that the rare earth oxide CeO₂ is broadly used in luminous materials, polishing powder, electronic ceramics and efficient catalyst in photocatalytic field. Ameta *et al.*¹¹ investigated the synthesis and characteriza-

tion of CeFeO_3 photocatalyst and its use in photocatalytic bleaching of gentian violet. Like other inorganic semiconductor photocatalysts, CeFeO_3 also acts as an inorganic semiconductor. It absorbs photons to create electron-hole pair, which can subsequently participate in the redox reaction. Kaur *et al.*¹² reported the synthesis and characterization of lanthanum cobalt oxide (La_2CoO_4) and its use as a photocatalyst for degradation of azure-B and yellowish orange. Jose *et al.*¹³ synthesized lanthanum chromium oxide and used it as a photocatalyst for the degradation of azure-B which is extensively used in printing and dyeing industries. La_2NiO_4 has been used for the photocatalytic degradation of yellowish orange dye¹⁴. Nanocubic $\text{La}_2\text{Sn}_2\text{O}_7$ photocatalyst with pyrochlore structure has been successfully synthesized by a one-pot hydrothermal method. Photocatalytic experiments showed that the $\text{La}_2\text{Sn}_2\text{O}_7$ samples not only had a high activity for degradation of methyl orange, but also the activity for generating H_2 with a rate of $39 \mu\text{mol/h}$ under ultraviolet light irradiation¹⁵.

La-doped ZnO has shown superior performance towards degradation and mineralization of 2,4,6-trichlorophenol, whereas very low photocatalytic activity was observed for undoped ZnO¹⁶. Photocatalytic activity of LaFeO_3 /montmorillonite nanocomposites was used for decolorization of rhodamine B in aqueous solution¹⁷. Photocatalytic activity of TiO_2 films and $\text{La}^{\text{III}}/\text{TiO}_2$ composite films were evaluated by photocatalytic decolorisation of methylene blue aqueous solution under the simulation of sunlight irradiation¹⁸.

Now-a-days the importance of photocatalytic processes has increased for the degradation of pollutants present in effluents. However, from the literature survey it has been observed that no attention has been paid on the use of lanthanum cerate as photocatalyst for the degradation of dye pollutants present in effluents. In the present work, nano-sized photocatalyst lanthanum cerate has been prepared by sol-gel method and used for the degradation of brilliant green (BG) under visible light. Brilliant green ($\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_2\cdot\text{HO}_4\text{S}$), is one of the triarylmethane dyes. The molecular weight of brilliant green dye is 482.65 and maximum wavelength of absorption is 623 nm. It is an organic dye and highly soluble in water giving green color solution. It is used in coloring silk and wool. It is also used in biological stain, dermatological agent and in poultry feed to prevent fungus formation. BG is

considered as highly toxic to both humans and animals since it causes irritation of respiration and gastrointestinal tracts leading to vomiting and diarrhoea. BG has been banned in many countries due to its carcinogenic nature¹⁹⁻²¹.

Fig. 1. Structure of brilliant green.

Experimental

Materials:

Lanthanum nitrate (Alfa Aesar 99.9%), cerium nitrate (Himedia), citric acid (Himedia), absolute alcohol and brilliant green (Himedia) were used in the present investigation. All the solution were prepared in double distilled water. All the chemicals were of analytical grade and used without further purification.

Citric acid assisted synthesis of nanoparticles of lanthanum cerate ($\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$):

For the synthesis of ternary photocatalyst, $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.1 M), $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.1 M) and citric acid (0.2 M) were dissolved in 30 mL mixture of H_2O and EtOH (1:1) to yield a homogeneous solution. The solution was stirred on magnetic stirrer for 1 h. The solution was stirred again at 70°C until it acquires homogeneous yellow coloured gel status. The gel is dried at 90°C for 24 h. The dried gel was grounded with the help of mortar and pestle. The grounded material was calcined at 600°C for 5 h with a heating rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and the final product was characterized by spectral analysis as $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$.

Citric acid forms chelate compounds with lanthanum and cerium. These complex ions are homogeneously distributed over the solution and during the gel formation too. It also acted as a fuel during calcination. A white spongy mass obtained after calcination is grinded to give fine powder of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of catalyst preparation.

Results and discussion

Characterization of La₂Ce₂O₇:

X-Ray diffraction method:

The ternary oxide was characterized by X-ray diffraction method. Fig. 3 describes the X-ray diffraction pattern of nano-sized La₂Ce₂O₇ photocatalyst. XRD diffraction pattern of the sample was recorded on XPERT-PRO diffractometer with Cu K α radiation. The accelerating voltage and the applied current were 35 kV and 20 mA, respectively. Diffraction pattern was recorded over the 2θ range from 10° to 90° with a step size of 0.0170°. The crystallite size (t) of the peak can be calculated by using Scherrer's formula: $t = 0.94\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$ where λ is the wavelength of X-rays used (1.5406 Å), β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) and θ is the angle of diffraction. The average crystallite size (or average particle size for the reported sample) of sample is found to be approximate 4.0 nm for all diffraction peaks. The intensity of

XRD peaks of the sample reflects that the formed nanoparticles are crystalline and broad diffraction peaks indicate very small crystallite size.

From the XRD graph, it is observed that the diffraction peaks are similar to cubic fluorite phase of CeO₂ (JCPDS file No. 01-089-8436)²². Furthermore, peaks corresponding to the individual oxides (La₂O₃ etc.) were not observed indicating the formation of La₂Ce₂O₇ solid solution formation. No evidence of La₂Ce₂O₇ pyrochlore phase (Fd₃m) was observed. The diffraction peaks with 2θ values at 28.12°, 32.42°, 46.62° and 55.81° can be well indexed to (111), (200), (220) and (311) planes of a cubic fluorite structure, respectively. These four intense peaks that correspond to the pure La₂Ce₂O₇ phase are also reported in the literature^{23–26}.

Energy dispersive spectroscopic (EDS) analysis:

EDS measurements were done for La₂Ce₂O₇ nanoparticles prepared by calcinations of the as synthesized product

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ nanoparticles.

Fig. 4. EDS spectrum of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$.

at 600°C for 5 h as shown in Fig. 4. The results obtained in atomic percentage for sample shows the stoichiometric chemical composition as $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$. There is 64.45% oxygen, 17.76% lanthanum and 17.79% cerium atoms present in the material, as observed by EDS result.

FESEM (Field emission scanning electron microscopy):

Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) images of synthesized $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ nano particles has been shown in Fig. 5. It was recorded on cold field emission electron microscope, Hitachi PU8010 at SAIF, Chandigarh. SEM gives the direct information about the size and structure of the synthesized $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ nanoparticles. The obtained particles are in the form of rice grain shape arranged densely in

homogeneous manner. As shown in the Fig. 5 (a), it is clear that the diameter size of the grain shape nanoparticles is about 14–28 nm. In Fig. 5(b) length size of rice like structure is 80–120 nm and thickness size is about 35–50 nm.

Fig. 5. FESEM images of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ nanoparticles.

TEM (Transmission electron microscopy) analysis:

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) studied by using Philips Tecnai 20 at SICART, Vallabh Vidyanagar, Anand. The morphology, particle size and structure of the synthesized $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ were examined by TEM. Fig. 6 illustrate the TEM images of the $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$, and the shape and size of particles resemble with the results obtained from XRD and FESEM.

Fig. 6. TEM images of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ nanoparticles.

FTIR (Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy) analysis:

FTIR analysis was performed by using Perkin-Elmer spectrum RX-I FTIR at SAIF, Chandigarh. Fig. 7 shows the FTIR spectrum of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ nanoparticles in the range $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Several characteristic absorption bands can be ob-

Fig. 7. FTIR spectrum of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ nanoparticles.

served at about $608, 741, 817, 861, 1040, 1080, 1193, 1318, 1422, 1628, 2509, 3425\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The intense signal detected at approximately 3400 cm^{-1} is an evidence for the presence of water molecules contained in the particles. The presence of the band near 3400 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ corresponds to the water molecule absorbed in the samples^{27,28}. In addition the band located at 1628 cm^{-1} represents another vibration of watermolecule²⁹. Bands between 1600 and 1000 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of nitrates³⁰. A peak with very weak intensity at 861 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the residual nitrate ion³¹.

Thermal gravimetry-differential thermal analysis:

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the as-prepared sample was studied from room temperature to 700°C at a heating rate of $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ under nitrogen atmosphere having a flow rate of $20\text{ mL}/\text{min}$. It was recorded on STA-6000 (DTA-TGA) Perkin-Elmer. Fig. 8(A) shows that the weight loss occurs in two stages, first stage taking place from room temperature up to 100°C , the weight loss during first stage occurs due to the evaporation of moisture. The weight loss during second stage from temperature 100°C up to 200°C occurs due to evaporation of nitrate and carbon (from unreacted ethanol and citric acid). Above 200°C the sample

is almost impurity free, which is observed from the graph. Fig. 8(B) shows the DTA curve for as-prepared sample. The two exothermic peaks at about 170°C and 200°C in the DTA curve correspond to the decomposition of unreacted citric acid and nitrates of lanthanum and cerium.

Fig. 8. TGA (a) and DTA (b) curves of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ nanoparticle.

Photocatalytic degradation of brilliant green:

Lanthanum cerate as photocatalyst has been used for the degradation of brilliant green dye. Stock solution of brilliant green ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) was prepared in doubly distilled water. A reaction mixture containing dye ($\approx 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) and 0.05

g photocatalyst was irradiated with a 200 W tungsten lamp (Philips). The progress of the dye degradation was monitored by measuring the absorbance of the reaction mixture at regular time intervals using UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Electronics India Model 2371) at 625 nm. The intensity of light from the lamp was measured using a Solarimeter (SM CEL 201). A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiations. A digital pH meter (Systronics Model 335) was used to measure the pH of the reaction mixture. The pH of the solution was adjusted by the addition of previously standardized 0.1 N H_2SO_4 and 0.1 N NaOH solutions. Different quality parameters for polluted and treated water were determined by using water analyser (Systronics Model 371).

It was observed that the absorbance of the dye solution decreases with the increasing time of exposure, which indicates that the concentration of brilliant green dye decreases with increasing time. A plot of $\log A$ versus time was linear following pseudo-first order kinetics. The rate constant was calculated with the expression: $k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$.

Effect of pH:

The effect of pH (Fig. 10) on the rate of degradation has been investigated in pH range 4.0–7.5 keeping all other parameters identical. It was observed that with an increase in pH, rate of reaction increases and after attaining the maxi-

Table 1. Typical run for photocatalytic degradation of brilliant green

Time (min)	$\log A$
0	1.011
10	0.925
20	0.876
30	0.842
40	0.792
50	0.742
60	0.684
70	0.635
80	0.589
90	0.507
100	0.468
110	0.401
120	0.351
Rate constant (k)	$2.11 \times 10^{-4} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$
[Brilliant green] = $1.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, Photocatalyst = 0.050 g, pH = 5.0, Light intensity = 50.0 mW cm^{-2} .	

Fig. 9. Typical run.

Fig. 10. Effect of pH variation.

imum value at pH 5.0, rate decreases with further increase in pH. The increase in the rate of photocatalytic degradation with increase in pH may due to more $O_2^{\cdot-}$ radicals, which are produced from the interaction of O_2 and electron (e^-) of the semiconductor. These $O_2^{\cdot-}$ radicals are protonated in acidic range of pH generating HO_2^{\cdot} radicals. These hydroperoxy radicals are responsible for the oxidative degradation of dye. After attaining optimum pH 5.0; the rate of reaction decreases because less number of HO_2^{\cdot} are available as pH approaches 7.0. Further increasing the pH, there will be no force of attraction between negatively charged surface of the semiconductor and neutral form of the dye.

This will result into a decrease in the rate of degradation. At lower pH also, the reaction rate decreases as there will be repulsion between a cationic dye and positively charged surface of the semiconductor.

Effect of concentration of dye:

The effect of variation of concentration of brilliant green (Fig. 11) on its degradation rate has been observed in the range from $0.5 \times 10^{-5} M$ – $3.5 \times 10^{-5} M$ keeping all other parameters identical. It has been observed that the rate of degradation increases with increasing concentration of dye up to $1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$. Further increase in concentration beyond this limit results in a decrease in degradation rate. This can be explained on the basis that, the reaction rate increases on increasing the concentration of dye, as more number of molecules of dyes were available but a further increase in concentration results appearing an internal filter effect which does not permit sufficient amount of light to reach the surface of the photocatalyst thus, decreasing the rate of photocatalytic degradation of brilliant green occurs.

Fig. 11. Effect of concentration of dye.

Effect of amount of catalyst:

The effect of variation of amount of catalyst (Fig. 12) on the rate of dye degradation has been observed in the range from 0.020 g to 0.090 g keeping other parameters identical. It is clear from the above data that with an increase in the amount of catalyst, the rate of degradation increases to a

Fig.12. Effect of amount of catalyst.

certain amount of catalyst, 0.050 g for $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$. Beyond this point, the rate of reaction decreases with increase in amount of catalyst.

This may be explained by the fact that with an increase in the amount of catalyst, the surface area of catalyst will also increase. Hence, the rise in the rate of reaction has been observed. But for further increase in the amount of catalyst beyond a limit (0.050 g), only the thickness of the layer (and not the exposed surface area) will increase at the bottom of reaction vessel, which was completely covered by the catalyst. This was also confirmed by using reaction vessels of different dimensions. It was observed that the point of saturation is shifted to a higher value for vessels of larger capacities while it is shifted to lower value for vessels of smaller capacities. As a result, less number of oxygen radicals is formed and consequently, reaction rate is retarded.

Effect of light intensity:

The effect of light intensity (Fig. 13) on rate of degradation of dye was also studied keeping all other parameters identical.

The effect of light intensity on the rate of degradation of brilliant green was also studied by varying the intensity of light from 10.0 to 70.0 mW cm^{-2} . The results indicate that with increasing light intensity, the rate of reaction increases and maximum rates were found at 50.0 mW cm^{-2} . It can be explained on the basis that as the intensity of light was increased, the number of photons striking per unit area also

Fig. 13. Effect of light intensity.

increases, resulting into higher rate of degradation for dye. Further increase in the intensity of light above 50.0 mW cm^{-2} may start some side thermal reactions and hence, higher light intensities have been avoided.

Mechanism:

On the basis of the experimental observations, a tentative mechanism has been proposed for the photocatalytic degradation (mineralization) of brilliant green in the presence of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$.

Brilliant green dye (BG) absorbs radiations of suitable wavelength and gives rise to its excited singlet state. Then it undergoes intersystem crossing (ISC) to give the triplet state of the dye. On the other hand, the semiconductor ($\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$) also absorbs light to excite an electron from its valence band (VB) to its conduction band (CB). This electron will be ab-

strated by oxygen molecule (dissolved oxygen) generating superoxide anion radical ($O_2^{\cdot-}$). This anion radical will be protonated in acidic medium and HO_2^{\cdot} radicals are produced. These HO_2^{\cdot} radicals will oxidize brilliant green dye to its leuco form, which may ultimately degrade to mineralized products (H_2O , CO_2).

The participation of HO_2^{\cdot} radicals was considered as an oxidant, because it was observed that degradation of brilliant green is not affected by the presence of OH^{\cdot} radical scavenger, isopropanol, which indicates OH^{\cdot} radicals are not playing any role in this degradation as an active oxidizing species in this reaction.

Water quality parameters:

Quality parameters of dye solution of brilliant green has been tested before and after its photocatalytic degradation by measuring some parameters like COD, DO, conductance, salinity, TDS and pH. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Water quality parameters

Various parameters studied	Before photocatalytic degradation	After photocatalytic degradation
COD (mg/L)	35.52	8.08
DO (ppm)	4.5	11.7
Conductance (μ S)	268	294
Salinity (ppt)	0.33	0.60
TDS (ppm)	148	166
pH	5.70	7.15

Chemical oxygen demand:

The mineralization of brilliant green was confirmed by measuring the decrease of COD value. COD of brilliant green dye solution was estimated before and after the photocatalytic treatment and the photodegradation efficiency of the catalyst was calculated from the following expression:

$$\eta = \frac{COD_{\text{before}} - COD_{\text{after}}}{COD_{\text{before}}} \times 100$$

η = Photodegradation efficiency (%), COD_{before} = COD of dye solution before illumination and COD_{after} = COD of dye solution after illumination.

Chemical oxygen demand of dye solutions before and after illumination has been determined volumetrically using $KMnO_4$ as an oxidant. The photodegradation efficiency after

2 h of illumination of brilliant green using nanoparticles of $La_2Ce_2O_7$ catalyst was found to be 77.25%.

Dissolved oxygen:

Dissolved oxygen analysis measures the amount of gaseous oxygen dissolved in aqueous solution. Increase in dissolved oxygen (from 4.5 ppm to 11.7 ppm) after photocatalytic degradation of the dye indicates mineralization of dye to a significant extent.

Conductance, salinity and TDS:

Conductivity as a summation parameter is a measure of the level of ionic concentration of solution. Conductivity parameter has been increased after the treatment because dye has been mineralized into ions like CO_3^{2-} , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} etc. Because of this reason, total dissolved solids (TDS) and salinity of the dye solution was also found greater after photocatalytic degradation of dye.

pH:

Before the treatment, pH of reaction mixture was in weak acid range, but after the degradation, pH becomes neutral because dye particles are mineralized to a significant extent.

Reusability:

Reusability of photocatalyst has been assessed. It has been found that photocatalyst can be used three times with almost same efficiency for the photocatalytic degradation of brilliant green.

Conclusions

Photocatalytic method is the most effective method for the treatment of wastewater. In the dark, the rate of photocatalytic reaction is slow, whereas on irradiation of reaction mixture with visible light, acceleration in the rate of degradation of dyes was observed. A nanoparticle of lanthanum cerate has been prepared by citric acid assisted sol-gel method. The degradation occurs efficiently over a wide pH range of 4.0–7.5. Good degradation efficiency of brilliant green in aqueous solution (77.25%) was achieved within 2 h reaction time. This catalyst has good stability for the degradation of brilliant green even after 3 cycles, and therefore, has a great potential. At optimal conditions, rate of degradation of brilliant green dye was found to be $k = 2.11 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. During photocatalytic process, HO_2^{\cdot} radicals react with dye and degrade it into smaller products like H_2O , CO_2 , NH_4^+ ions etc.

The kinetics of the photodegradation in the presence of the nanocatalyst $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ follows pseudo-first order rate model. Radical mechanism for degradation has been confirmed by using radical scavenger isopropanol.

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